

Local Government in Croatia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Dario Runtic

NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe
with the support of the Association of Cities in the Republic of Croatia

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Croatia: An Introduction

Dario Runtic, *NALAS Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Allocation of responsibilities among urban local governments (ULGs), rural local governments (RLGs) and regional governments in Croatia is set in Article 129(a) of the Constitution and further elaborated in the Organic Law on Local and Regional Governments and various sectoral laws. The key criteria for the allocation of responsibilities are the number of inhabitants and the level of sub-national government.

All local governments, whether urban or rural, carry out tasks referring to organization of settlement and housing; spatial and urban planning; utility services; child-care; primary health protection; social welfare; elementary education; culture, physical culture and sports; consumer protection; environment protection; fire and civil protection; maintenance of municipal roads and traffic management.

Large towns, above 30,000 inhabitants, and the towns in which a regional government has a seat, have additional responsibilities related to the maintenance of local public roads and construction permits, in addition to those listed above. The regional governments execute these functions on behalf of the smaller towns and municipalities.

In case of specific services there could be an additional limitation in place for provision of a specific service, such as minimum number of inhabitants for, e.g., management of elementary education.

The scope of counties' responsibilities can be self-managing and entrusted (government affairs). Counties are tasked with performing the following tasks: general public administration services; primary and secondary education; healthcare; regional and urban planning; economic development; environmental protection; transport and traffic infrastructure; management of the network of educational, medical, social welfare, and cultural institutions; administration pertaining to agriculture, forestry, mining, and industry; management of road transport infrastructure; construction permitting, excluding the area of large towns and a county seat city.

Re-assignment of responsibilities between individual local and regional governments is allowed pending approval of the representative bodies of both government units. Certain restrictions apply such as the ability to fund a specific responsibility (in case of most of responsibilities).

Local governments can provide services themselves, through institutions established by local governments, through local government owned enterprises or by entrusting public services to private operators through public procurement contracts or concessions.

Local governments typically provide general services related to all responsibilities within the nationally imposed legal framework – organization of services, contracting, funding, planning and taxation. They also provide organization of settlement and housing, spatial planning services, construction permitting, business permitting and provision of social welfare benefits. Institutions established by local governments provide child care, health protection, social welfare services, elementary education, culture, and fire protection. Local government owned enterprises mostly perform utility services, environment protection and maintenance of roads and infrastructure. Public procurement contracts and concessions are mostly used for infrastructure construction and maintenance, waste management, public lighting, public transport, parking and green market management. Public-private contracts for public service provision have been implemented in areas of sport and education, however, this form of public service provision is not widespread due to downfalls of early public-private partnership (PPP) contracts.

Local governments are also allowed to carry out their responsibilities through various forms of inter-municipal cooperation, be it joint administrative departments, companies or institutions. The General Local Government Act enables voluntary inter-municipal cooperation, but leaves it up to participating local governments to set all terms of cooperation in a cooperation agreement. There are no mandatory inter-municipal cooperation arrangements in provision of services.

Although the Constitution defines responsibilities which are within autonomous scope of local governance, the sectoral legislation limits the extent to which local governments are autonomous in carrying out those functions. Local and/or regional governments are entrusted with partial responsibilities and often required to obtain approvals from other levels of governments. E.g. in primary education, local governments are responsible for capital investment, maintenance and operating expenses (insufficiently funded through grants for decentralized functions) while the government funds teachers' wages. In terms of firefighting, local governments have broader responsibilities but are required to seek approval for the appointment of fire chief, fire protection plans, and other basic decisions from other levels of government. RLGs face broader restrictions than ULGs although the autonomous scope of ULG and RLG is basically the same. The gap between the constitutional provisions and the actual performance is caused by governmental centralization of most of the functions during the time of the 1990 Homeland War and structural fragmentation of local governments at the same time. Some responsibilities were partially decentralized in the 2000's (education, firefighting, social welfare, healthcare) and 2008-2010 (road maintenance, construction permitting). The gap still remains due to high fragmentation of local government and government's mostly unchallenged method of operation. Lately this principle has been tested before the Constitutional Court and, pending decision, may change the intergovernmental relations in future.

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